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Actual Tasks of Teaching Russian as a Foreign Language

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ABSTRACT

The article is devoted to the analysis of current tasks of modern linguodidactics in the sphere of teaching Russian as a foreign language (RaFL). As the main directions of its further improvement the author indicates effective systematization of speech material, adjustment of the linguistic component of training courses and coordination of educational resources, as well as enrichment of the content of the training base. Speech skills are an important component of the content of teaching Russian as a foreign language. In the process of mastering Russian, it is difficult for foreigners to differentiate speech patterns in accordance with different communication situations. Therefore, a condition of effective learning is the systematization of functionally authentic speech material, in other words the creation of a communicative fund. The author offers an effective method of speech means systematization which fully corresponds to the objectives of language teaching practice and is based on the consecutive description of communicative-pragmatic complexes. Communicative-pragmatic complex is understood as a block, combining speech acts similar in function with the corresponding intentions, communicative situations and speech models. When describing consistently systematically, the complex covers all basic stereotypical situations, in which a typical intention in speech practice is realized. As a rule, the communicative-pragmatic complex combines three or four typical communicative situations, reflecting the real communication in Russian. The article also emphasizes the need for a stricter alignment of lexical minimums with the norms of the corresponding levels of Russian language proficiency, the need to include more interesting texts about modern Russia, to show the attractive features of modern Russians - interest in education, sports, travel, healthy lifestyles, outdoor recreation, festivals of student songs, bard songs, etc.

Keywords: *Russian as a Foreign Language, Teaching Principles, Communicative-Pragmatic Complex*

Introduction

The modern state of linguodidactics in the field of foreign language teaching is characterized by the search for new approaches and objects of scientific reflection and new tasks. They are conditioned by the new realities of the 21st century - rapid globalization, the spread of new technical possibilities of teaching foreign languages and, accordingly, the appearance of new

learning environments, the digitalization of communication, the use of distance learning, etc. All these aspects are actively discussed at numerous international conferences and in the literature.

Foreign language learning is a complex process, and its success depends on many components: on the interest of the learners themselves, on the educational environment, on the educational resources and teaching technologies, on the systematization of the language material, etc. A foreign language learning environment is defined as the implementation of appropriate teaching approaches that contribute to the regular practice of improving the foreign language on the part of learners. The modern learning process has transformed students from passive objects of learning into active subjects, capable not only under the guidance of the teacher, but also to acquire the necessary knowledge independently and effectively organize their educational activities (Makhmudzhanovna, 2022). The efficiency of self-learning is increased by using distance learning programs. To implement the tasks in this direction, it is proposed to optimize the work with bilingual students through the use of existing educational distance learning platforms (Savilova, Kropotkina, Kokhanovskaya, 2021). An important task of distance learning is to maintain and enhance students' motivation to learn. The literature considers communication parameters affecting successful learning: designation of communication goals, a greater degree of explicit expression of information, exchange of signals of understanding or misunderstanding, flexibility of communicative distance, emotional support of the communication partner (Karasik, 2022). The primary important purpose of the existence of any languages is the use of their performance of socio-communicative functions. Using English as an example, the factors influencing the effective use of language not only in the classroom but also outside the classroom in real social situations, both oral and written, are investigated to assess the effectiveness of the language learning and teaching process (Nguyen, 2021).

The development of linguodidactic theory in the field of teaching Russian as a foreign language is characterized by significant efforts of methodologists, psychologists, linguists, teachers. The methodology of teaching Russian as a foreign language (RaFL) has come a long way in seven decades: leading centers for teaching RaFL have been created at MSU, SPbSU, PFUR (Peoples' Friendship University of Russia), A.S. Pushkin Russian Language Institute; psycholinguistic and methodological bases for teaching Russian as a foreign language, based on theoretical and methodological achievements of modern Russian studies, have been compiled by linguists, the State Educational Standard for RaFL, in which for every foreign language the state educational standard was developed and put into practice, has been developed (Shchukin, 2003). Such a scale of linguodidactics promotion in the sphere of teaching the Russian language testifies to the real interest in the Russian language in the world, and to the considerable efforts of teachers of Russian. At the same time, the current state of the methodology of teaching the RaFL suggests possible vectors for its improvement, which can be summarized in the following aspects: the effective systematization of speech material, the adjustment of the linguistic component of the Russian language courses, the consistent coordination of teaching resources, the enrichment of the content of the teaching base. Let us consider them in more detail.

The aim of this work is to show the actual tasks of teaching Russian as a foreign language as the author sees them. Speech skills are an important component of the content of teaching

Russian as a foreign language. In the process of mastering Russian, it is difficult for foreigners to differentiate speech patterns in accordance with different communication situations. Therefore, a condition of effective learning is the systematization of functionally authentic speech material, in other words the creation of a communicative fund. The author offers an effective method of speech means systematization which fully corresponds to the objectives of language teaching practice and is based on the consecutive description of communicative-pragmatic complexes. When describing consistently systematically, the complex covers all basic stereotypical situations, in which a typical intention in speech practice is realized.

To show the specifics of the means of expression of the communicative intentions of support, joy, consent, request, etc., representative material was collected in Russian, typified and grouped into communicative-pragmatic complexes that were described and compared with the typical means of expression of these intentions in languages characterized by nominative analyticism - in English and Bulgarian. A comprehensive step-by-step comparative system-functional approach to the study of the original and translated texts was used, involving the following stages of analysis:

- 1) comparative semantic-contextual analysis of the original Russian and English and Bulgarian translated texts;
- 2) classification and quantitative characterization of the samples;
- 3) identification of the most regular, typical means of expression of the considered communicative intentions;
- 4) description of the structure of communicative-pragmatic complexes and typical means of their expression.

The requirements of the standard and the lexical minimum of the basic level of Russian language proficiency were also subjected to a special analysis.

Linguistic paradigms and the problem of speech media grouping

Modern linguistics develops in different, coexisting and interacting directions and feeds foreign language teaching methodology with different methods and technologies for classifying speech material. In the systemocentric paradigm, the aim of which is to taxonomize grammatical and lexical units, the means of expressing various communicative intentions are mentioned in connection with the characterization of the syntax of simple sentences by the purpose of utterance and the characteristics of sentence members - definition, purpose circumstances, cause, mode of action, etc.

The purpose of the functional paradigm is to determine the functions possessed by linguistic units. In functional grammar, the means of expressing various senses - temporality, locality, causality, etc. - are described in connection with the characteristics of functional-semantic fields, within the boundaries of which they are systematized depending on the specific semantics. The functional-communicative approach implies connecting the analysis of language units in the direction from semantics to means of expression and from forms to their semantics. The concept of functional grammar in the functional-semantic direction is implemented on a large scale in the works of A.V. Bondarko and his followers (Bondarko, 1976).

The purpose of the cognitive paradigm is to establish connections between mental structures and language units. One of the most actively developed areas of modern linguocognitivism is conceptology. In the cognitive paradigm, the means of expressing certain intentions are clarified by the discursive characterization of the corresponding conceptosphere.

The purpose of the communicative-pragmatic paradigm is to establish the patterns of language units use in certain communicative situations (Passov, 1991). The material for it is the natural speech of native speakers in typical communicative situations. Communicative linguistics does not aim at fixing and describing all units used in speech. It fixes the typical models. In the communicative-pragmatic paradigm, based on the theory of speech acts by J. Austin (Austin, 1985) and J. Searle (Searle, 1986), Russian linguistics develops principles for describing speech units, taking into account the conditions of their use in the acts of speech communication. The integral and developed theory of speech acts has developed within the framework of linguistic philosophy under the influence of L. Wittgenstein's ideas about the multiplicity of the purposes of language and their inseparability from life forms. The core of the theory of speech acts, as is well known, consists of the ideas expounded by the English logician J. Austin in his lecture course given at Harvard University in 1955 and published later on. Subsequently, these ideas were developed by the American logician J. Searle in his monograph «Speech Acts» and a number of articles. Speech act theory proceeds from the fact that the unit of communication is not a sentence or any other linguistic expression, but the performance of a certain kind of communicative action, such as, for example, statement, request, question, order, expression of gratitude, apology, congratulation, etc. The object of research in the theory of speech acts is the act of speech, which consists in the speaking of a statement in a situation of direct communication with the listener (works of M. V. Vsevolodova, V. G. Gak, V. B. Evtyukhin, G. A. Zolotova, E. I. Passov, N. I. Formanovskaya, etc.). The conditions for the use of speech units include the roles of: the speaking subject, the addressee, their interaction, the situation of communication; explicit and implicit goals of the statement; speech tactics and types of speech behavior; indirect meanings of the statement, hints; pragmatic presuppositions, etc. (Arutyunova, 1990).

Pragmatics studies speech actions in the communicative pragmatic space - the zone where language fixes the diverse relations of the speaker to reality, his communicative intentions, which are perceived and recognized by the addressee (Vezbitskaya, 1985; Formanovskaya, 2002). The focus in lingvopragmatics is put forward communicative, pragmatically determined, intentions of speakers.

Thus, there is no single, generally accepted, universal strategy for the systematization of speech means, the search is conducted by researchers from different sides. They describe communicative-pragmatic fields, communicative intentions, speech acts, dialogical unities, etc.

Modern RaFL teaching methodology is based on a comprehensive approach to the analysis of speech activity, evaluating as the leading communicative approach and the methodological principles arising from this approach. Thus, the principle of communicative orientation of teaching focuses the teacher on the formation of students' motivated need for speech communication in the language, on the organization of the course in accordance with the social

and communicative profile of students, on the communicative nature of grammar, vocabulary, assignments and exercises. The principle of dynamic deployment of speech activity implies the structure of the RaFL course with sequential expansion and complication of the teaching material, aimed at the formation of skills and abilities of speech communication and their gradual coordinated multiplication.

The requirement for a gradual increase in the content of abilities, skills, and language competences of foreign students is also set by the State Standards for Russian as a Foreign Language, which regulate the content of students' competences at different levels of RaFL proficiency. Thus, at the basic level students become familiar with the means of expressing the most regular intentions (desire, request, offer, invitation, consent/disagreement, refusal). They master the imperative forms of the most frequently used verbs in everyday communication (*дай/дайте* - give; *возьми/возьмите* - take), incentive sentences (*Пойдемте в кафе* - *Let's go to a cafe*), the range of models is expanded and the means of expressing a wish, intention, advice, permission or prohibition are practiced. The standard of the first level of possession adds the intentions of attracting attention, interrogation, prompting for a dialogue. The standard of the second level aims at mastering the blocks of speech intentions, regulating interaction, and evaluative intentions. The third level of Russian language proficiency includes the ability to verbally implement contact-establishing, regulating, informative, and evaluative intentions and the ability to demonstrate their complex use. Thus, the State Standard of the Russian language assumes a stage-by-stage increase in the content of abilities, skills, and language competences of foreign students, a dynamic deployment of the basics of speech activity, detailed speech skills and their generalization.

Principles of systematization of linguistic means in communicative-pragmatic complexes (CPC)

In my opinion, an effective methodology for the systematization of linguistic means, meeting the objectives of the practice of teaching the RaFL, can be built on the basis of a consistent description of communicative-pragmatic complexes (Karpenko, 2017). By communicative-pragmatic complex we mean a block uniting speech acts close in function with the corresponding intentions, communicative situations and speech models. In a consistent systematic description CPC covers all the basic stereotypical situations in which in the speech practice some typical intentions are realized: gratitude, joy, support, approval, consent, complaint, etc. With this approach the researcher determines the totality of single-type communicative situations, in which some common, typical meaning is expressed. Then those aspects of situations are identified that cause a change in the model of speech expression of the common meaning, and speech models are described in detail. As a rule, communicative-pragmatic complex unites three or four typical communicative situations, reflecting the real communication in Russian.

In the terminological field of communicative linguistics there are concepts that meaningfully correlate with the proposed concept of communicative-pragmatic complex, such as frame models of communication, speech acts, dialogical unities, speech intentions. However, each of them is occupied by its own specific, narrower, content. Thus, a frame model of communication is a

frame image of a specific situation, for example: library, an announcement for readers. Speech act is any single act of speech, consisting in the utterance of a statement by the addressee (*Сдаете книги?*- *Do you turn in your books?*). The primary form of realization of language activity is dialogic speech. Dialogical unity is a set of two adjacent replicas in a particular situation (*Сдаете книги? – Хочу еще продлить.*-*Are you turning in books? - I want to prolong more*). Speech intention is the semantic basis of a separate statement, which determines the task of the communicative act, its intent.

Communicative-pragmatic complex is a more capacious structural and content unity than each of the above. Its purpose is to present types of communicative situations, corresponding to them speech intentions and typical speech models, in which in the speech practice a typical intention is realized. When describing it systematically, it covers the main stereotypical situations, makes it possible to present them comprehensively and show their characteristic models. The notion of communicative-pragmatic complex in the presence of a number of correlated notions (such as speech act, dialogical unity, communicative situation, communicative intention, etc.) and in the absence of their organizing structure is designed to play a systemic role in the RaFL methodology, organize speech patterns, and thus demonstrate the complex and multidimensional nature of real communication. Let us further consider the organization of the material on the example of several communicative-pragmatic complexes.

III.I. Communicative-pragmatic complex «Support» in Russian speech practice is realized in three typical situations: 1) support in action; 2) psychological support in a stressful situation; 3) dialogic support of consent.

As a speech act of a special type, the speech act of support is made in certain conditions and according to certain rules, has a certain intention, purpose. In all types of communicative situations as a result of the reaction of support is such an impact on the consciousness, state or behavior of the interlocutor, which creates a new situation. This allows us to classify the speech act of support as both illocutionary and perlocutionary.

III.I. 1. When expressing support in an action, the speaker encourages the interlocutor, stimulates him or her to continue the action begun, which is often accompanied by an approving evaluation of the action itself (*Давай-давай! Дело хорошее.* – *Come on, come on! It's a good thing*). The speaker's expressed approval of the interlocutor's action stimulates him to continue the action, but more actively, more confidently. Agreeing with the interlocutor, corresponding to the third case, is also an expression of support, and support in this manifestation is observed most often. In these situations, the Russian speech practice is absolutely dominated by the imperative definite-personal sentences with the predicate in the form of an imperative in the 2nd person singular or plural of verbs of active action. They usually form a single line with repeated verbs: *Работай(те)! Работай(те)! - Work! Work!; Пишите(те)! Пишите(те)! - Write! Write!* etc.

III.I.2. The need for psychological support arises in the case of a problematic life situation of the addressee, causing feelings associated with separation or with some kind of worldly failure, loss. The main means of expressing psychological support are also the prompts with the predicate in the form of the 2nd person singular or plural of imperative of verbs with the semantics of calmness (*Успокойся!/Успокойтесь!* - *Calm down!*; *Мужайся!/Мужайтесь!*-*Courage!*

etc.), as well as verbs of emotional experience with the negation (*Не расстраивайся!/Не расстраивайтесь!* - *Don't get upset!*; *Не волнуйся/Не волнуйтесь!* - *Don't worry!* *Не беспокойся!/Не беспокойтесь!* - *Don't worry!* *Не переживай!/ Не переживайте!* - *Don't worry!*). Less expressive and less frequent are impersonal sentences with the predicate expressed by the impersonal form *не стоит*+ infinitive—doesn't cost+ infinitive (*Не стоит волноваться.* - *Don't worry;* *Не стоит беспокоиться* - *It is not worth worrying;* *Не стоит унывать* - *Not worth getting discouraged*). Questioning impersonal sentences with a predicate expressed by the impersonal form *стоит*+infinitive also weakly convey psychological support: *Стоит ли волноваться? Стоит ли беспокоиться?* - *Is it worth worrying? Is it worth worrying about?*

III.I.3. Dialogical support of agreement takes place in a dialogue and is a response of the speaker(s) to the speech, the interlocutor's replica: *Согласен с Вами* - *I agree with you;* *Вы правы* - *You are right;* *Я тоже так считаю* - *I think so too*, and so on. For the dialogical support of agreement the replicas with non unit sentences, which convey the emotional modal-evaluation reaction of the speaker, are typical: *Точно.* - *Exactly;* *Конечно.* - *Of course;* *Действительно.* - *Indeed;* *Правильно!* - *That's right!*; *Да, да! Вот, вот!* - *Yes, yes!*

The organization of speech patterns, corresponding to a certain complex in the focus not only communicative, but also comparative approach allows us to show the systemicity of speech means and their national-language specificity in the interpretation of certain typical situations. Thus, for example, in English, unlike in Russian, there is no such structural-semantic type among one-part sentences as impersonal sentences, so two-part sentences with a real or desemantized subject and infinitive are frequent here: *You don't have to worry;* *There is nothing to worry about;* *It is not necessary to worry.* The lexical markers of the situation here, on the contrary, are uniparental; as a rule, it is the verb *to worry*. The great stereotypicality of the models of expression of support is also due to the absence in English of a formal distinction between *you* sing. and *you* plural.

Significant differences can also be found when comparing with the Slavic languages. For example, in Bulgarian there is no infinitive, so here in speech practice, along with the imperative with the negation of the reflexive verbs (*притеснявам се* - *to worry;* *тревожа се* - *to worry*) *Не се притеснявай!* - *Don't worry!*; *Не се тревожи!* - *Don't worry!*) the use of the da-construction is possible. It is obligatory when translating Russian expressions with the infinitive: *Не стоит беспокоиться* - *Не струва да се притесняваш;* *Стоит ли беспокоиться?* - *Струва ли да се притесняваш?*

III.II. Communicative and pragmatic complex «Joy» in the Russian speech practice is also realized in three typical situations: joy in the situation of meeting, empathy of joy with the interlocutor, joy about the events carried out in the interests of the speaker. Despite the stereotype of the basic models, it is evident that certain situations and the expressed intentions are fixed by means typical for them (*Рад видеть Вас.* - *Glad to see you;* *Рад встретиться с Вами.* - *Glad to meet you;* *Рад её приезду* - *Glad to see her coming*). The comparative method fixes their national-language specificity. For example, in the situation "joy in the situation of meeting" in Russian the words of the state category are used (*Рад* - *Glad;* *Рады* - *Glad;* *Приятно* - *Pleased*) with the dependent infinitive (*Рад познакомиться* - *Glad to meet you;*

Рад тебѣ видѣть – *Glad to see you*; *Рад Вас приветствовать* – *Glad to greet you*). In Bulgarian in this situations the verbal way of deployment of the predicative group with the personal form of the reflexive verb with the dependent da-construction (*Радвам се да се запозная. Радвам се да те видя. Радвам се да Ви приветствувам*).

III.III. Communicative-pragmatic complex "Consent" is realized in communicative situations of three types: consent in response to a question, consent in response to stimulus to action, consent as reaction to information. The most typical means of expressing consent in a question-answer situation are elliptical replies, exclamatory sentences (*А как же! Еще бы! – And how! You bet!*), the word-proposal (*Да.–Yes.*), modal words. In the situation of reaction to the incitement to action the main means of agreement are replicas with affirmative particles (*Хорошо. Ладно.– Good. Okay*), with verb forms in the present or future tense (*Иду.–I'm coming; Сделаю. – I'll do it*), with adverbs of time that convey readiness for action (*Сейчас. – Now; Уже иду. – Already going*). In the situation of agreement with information replicas with modal words in predicative function (*Правда. –True; Верно. – True; Точно. – Accurate*) are typical.

III.IV. Communicative-pragmatic complex "Inducement" is also represented by three basic types depending on the modality of inducement and the degree of its intensity within the subfields of categorical inducement (demand, prohibition, order, command, order), neutral (advice, invitation, wish, warning, permission, offer) and mitigated inducement (request, pleading, persuasion, entreaty). The presentation of linguistic means to foreign students according to the mentioned three types will contribute to the clearest understanding of the peculiarities of the expression of inducement intentions and the formation of correct communicative competences. Let us further consider the means of expression of mitigated inducement - "Request". The request is distinguished by the fact that the commission of the action is thought in the interests of the speaker. Speech act of request does not imply the obligation of execution/non-execution of the action by the addressee, the desire of the speaker to induce the addressee to act is based on an internal personal motive. The request most often comes from the person whose social status is lower, and is directed to the person whose social status is higher, or is characterized by the absence of subordinate relations. As a rule, when expressing a request, the speaker seeks to state its reasons and motives.

Characteristic linguistic means are expressed by asking forms of imperative verbs denoting the desired action. They are usually accompanied by etiquette formulas of politeness or additional explanation (*Скажи, пожалуйста! –Tell me, please!; Скажи мне, прошу тебя! – Tell me, please!; Принеси, пожалуйста! – Fetch, please!; Принеси, пожалуйста, прошу тебя! – Fetch, please!*). In statements with the semantics of a request, indicators of politeness may be used: particles *«пожалуйста»*, *«только»*, *«хоть»*, *«уж»*, *«-ка»*, as well as introductory elements such as *«будьте добры, будьте любезны»* – be kind; *«ради Бога»* – for God's sake; *«прошу Вас»* – please, *«сделайте одолжение»* – do me a favor and the like. The particle *«пожалуйста»* – please is a regular mean of expressing a polite attitude of any speaker to any listener, regardless of their social status. *«Пожалуйста»* is used not only when expressing a request, but also in the realization of other modal shades of inductive semantics. In

addition, the addressee of the request can be characterized by evaluative definitions such as «дорогой, дорогая» – dear, darling etc.: *Дорогая, разреши мне ненадолго отлучиться. – Darling, let me go away for a while.*

In official communication the typical form of expression of a request is the construction «*прошу* + infinitive», less frequently «*разреши* + infinitive» is used: *Прошу уточнить* - *Please clarify*; *Прошу объяснить* – *Please explain*; *Прошу рассмотреть мою кандидатуру* – *Please consider my candidacy*, etc.

The meaning of the request can also be expressed through the subjunctive: *Я попросил бы* – I would ask; *Сходил бы ты* – Would you go. Another frequent form of request is the interrogative sentence: *Ты не скажешь мне, когда уйдет поезд?* – *Will you tell me when the train is leaving?*; *Вы не знаете, сколько еще осталось ребят в лагере?* – *Do you know how many kids are left in the camp?* In situations that are especially important to the speaker, the request can turn into a plea or an entreaty: *Я вас умоляю, не бросайте трубку, выслушайте!* *Дай, умоляю!* – *I'm begging you, don't hang up, listen! Give, I beg you!*

III.V. Communicative-pragmatic complex "State of affairs clarification" finds expression in questions: 1) about the general state of the interlocutor; 2) about his specific life circumstances, plans; 3) about the state of affairs of others: *Как ты?* – *How are you?*; *Как твои дела?* – *How are you?*; *Как жизнь?* – *How are you?*; *Как самочувствие?* – *How do you feel?*; *Как работа?* – *How is your work?*; *Как твои планы?* – *How are your plans* ; *Как семья?* – *How's your family?*; *Как твои родители?* – *How are your parents?*; *Как дети?* – *How are the kids?* It is conveyed by sentences with the question word «*Как?*» – *How?*. The comparative method shows the specificity of the lexical and grammatical design of such speech models of the Russian language. First, this complex demonstrates the universality of the model with the nominative case. Secondly, it reveals the functional flexibility of the Russian case system: *Как Иван?* = *Как у Ивана?* *Как Ивану?* *Как с Иваном?* The corresponding English and Bulgarian models are comparable to the Russian one, but are limited by the possibilities of grammar, characterized by name analyticism in these languages.

The use of the comparative approach accompanies the process of model assimilation with the necessary commentary on the characteristic features of the studied language, such as, for example, the prevalence of infinitive single-unit sentences in Russian when expressing the intentions of a variety of CPC (gratitude, support, warning, threatening, fearing, etc.): *Как мне Вас благодарить?* – *How should I thank you?*; *Как же быть?* – *What should I do?*; *Что же делать?* – *What should I do?*; *Не стоит волноваться.* – *You don't have to worry*; *Не нужно смущаться.* – *You don't have to be embarrassed*; *Нужно держать себя в руках.* – *You need to keep yourself in check*; *Быть тебе битым.* – *You should be beaten and under.* The means of expressing certain intents depend on the lexical and grammatical systemic features of the languages. Comparison with Bulgarian shows that in the absence of the infinitive and the corresponding variety of impersonal sentences in similar situations Bulgarian speech practice uses definite-fixed or indefinite-fixed sentences with a yes-construction or personal forms of the verb: *Как мога да Ви благодаря?* *Какво да правим?* *Не трябва да се притесняваш.* *Необходимо е да се държиш в ръцете.* *Ще те бият* and so on.

Adjustment and better coordination of teaching resources

In teaching a foreign language, along with the principle of freedom of creativity, which is manifested in orientation on communicativeness, pragmatism, there is a requirement unifying the teaching of a foreign language - the principle of standardization of foreign language teaching. The development of standards contributes to the improvement of foreign language teaching. As a prerequisite for standardization of foreign language instruction was the unification of terminological differences characteristic of the 1970s-80s. Unification is realized in the synchronization of teaching methods, materials, programs, forms, and methods of evaluation through clear and realistic goals "reflected" in the levels of proficiency in a particular language.

The National Language Standard serves as the main linguistic and methodological guide for teachers of the RaFL, it describes the main educational requirements related to the goals and content of learning at each stage of language teaching. The clarity of the standards contributes to the improvement of foreign language instruction. Thus, the Standard of the basic level assumes acquaintance with the means of expressing the most regular intentions (desire, request, offer, consent/disagreement, refusal). The Standard of the first level adds intentions of attracting attention, interrogation, prompting to dialogue. The second level standard aims at mastering the blocks of speech intentions regulating interaction. The third level adds informative and evaluative intentions, and the ability to demonstrate the complex use of these. Thus, the State Standard of the RaFL assumes a stage-by-stage deployment of the basics of speech activity, detailing of speech skills. The teacher of RaFL must know the communicative themes and situations defined by level standards and strive not to go beyond a certain level.

Grammar is the most complexly organized part of the language system and the most difficult for foreign students to master. On the other hand, grammar is a kind of the brain center of language, without the support of grammar full acquisition of a foreign language is impossible. In selecting grammatical material, the teacher of RaFL follows a number of principles derived from the communicative approach. These principles: communicative necessity and sufficiency, methodological expediency, grammatical minimum, situational and thematic principle of course structure, etc. Grammatical material requires strict dosage, coordination with communicative situations and topics at each specific level. Thus, one of the very first grammatical topics – «Plural nouns» – should not be explained within the lexical topic «Family», containing a group of ancient lexical units, the variability of word change of which is incomprehensible from the point of view of the current state of Russian language and requires a historical comment. They reflect base accretions (*мать – матери, дочь – дочери*), historical alternations (*сестра – сёстры, отец–отцы*) or ancient unproductive endings (*сын – сыновья, брат – братья, зять – зятья*). The plural of nouns is justified on the material of vocabulary whose plural forms are formed according to productive models: *факультет – факультеты, студент – студенты, стол – столы, учебник – учебники; комната – комнаты, парта – парты, книга– книги* etc. This grammatical specificity prompts the coordination of the grammatical theme «Plural nouns» with the lexical theme «On the lesson».

We can talk about the adjustment of teaching materials on the example of the topics of case compounding of names, variant endings, word formation and morphemics, which also require consideration of historical processes in Russian: errors in the definition of roots, suffixes and endings can be seen sometimes in the textbooks. The content of the standard in terms of verb classes requires methodological clarification. The standard of the basic level lists 17 verb classes as necessary for learning grammatical material: 1: *читать – читаю*, 2: *уметь – умею*; 3: *чувствовать – чувствую*; 4: *встретить – встречу*; 5: *отдохнуть – отдохну*; 6: *давать – дают*; 7: *ждать – ждут*; 8: *писать – пишут*; 9: *петь – поют*; 10: *мочь – могут*; 11: *идти – идут*; 12: *ехать – едут*; 13: *хотеть – хотят*; 14: *брать – берут*; 15: *жить – живут*; 16: *пить – пьют*; 17: *есть – едят* (Nakhabina, 2001, p.14). It is hardly necessary to have such a long list of non-productive classes at the basic level, since many classes do not contain the verbs in use. But the lexical minimum clearly suffers from an incomplete vocabulary (Lexical Minimum "Russian as a foreign language"). We can't do without the verbs *отдохнуть*, *болеть*, *мочь*, *жить* at the basic level working on topics such as: «About Myself», «My Family», «My Day», «Health», and situations such as: «At the health center», «At the doctor's office», etc. The vocabulary of the lexical minimum requires a stricter consideration of the topics recommended by the standard and the standard requires a strict dosage of grammatical material. It seems that not only foreign, but also Russian students are not ready at the initial stage to learn all the regularities of conjugation. It is no coincidence that domestic grammarians write about the exceptional diversity of verbal conjugation, stating that the complexity of the picture concerning the structure of the verb base itself. In this situation, recommendations on how to teach and learn Russian verb classes in basic level RaFL lessons are obvious: teach verb conjugation of non-productive classes from the communicative approach - to teach verb types in a communicative way. For example, the verb *болеть*, which is not mentioned in the lexical minimum, is needed in the basic level topic "Health" and in the situation "At the doctor's office". Along with this verb it is necessary to take into account the vocabulary that is steadily used in this situation in the speech patterns typical for the Russian language: *Я болею – У меня болит голова /в голове гудит, в ушах звенит, в боку колет... У меня кашель – Я кашляю; У меня температура – Я температуру, etc.*

Extension of the content-based learning base

The task of the teacher of Russian as a foreign language is not only to teach foreign students systematic features of grammar and vocabulary of the Russian language, norms of word usage, types of speech activity, but also to introduce them to the world of Russian culture, knowledge of which allows you to understand the nature and way of life of the Russians, adapt in Russia. According to A.N. Shchukin, country study is "a basic science for methodology, the subject of which is a set of information about the country of the language being studied. Country study information provides not only cognitive, but also communicative needs of students, contributing to the formation of communicative competence (Shchukin, 2003). In addition to teaching the

norms of modern Russian speech, the methodology of teaching RaFL should focus more attention on the cultural aspect.

A review of the existing teaching complexes shows that cultural aspects in modern Russian-language teaching practice can be enriched with interesting modern material; a lot of textbooks are exemplary in this regard, including those by acknowledged experts in this field: V. G. Kostomarov, L. S. Zhuravleva, Y. M. Naumenko and others. The most successful in terms of a variety of culturological material, well-thought-out structure, the use of effective methods of its presentation remain Soviet textbooks: «Russian Language for Everyone» prepared and published under the editorship of V. G. Kostomarov (1987) and «Russian language: A practical course: Textbook for beginners» by L. S. Zhuravleva (1989). A. Bragina's «Vocabulary of the language and culture of the country» (1981). There is also a modern specialized textbook in cultural studies for students of Russian as a foreign language N.V. Basko «Getting to know the Russian traditions and life of the Russians», «Textbook on Russian language and cultural studies» (Basko, 2014). The main purpose of this textbook is to acquaint foreigners with Russian traditions and customs, peculiarities of behavior of Russian people in different communicative situations and with their mentality. The texts on the pages of this textbook, as well as proverbs, proverbs and phrases, which are the key to understanding and revealing the Russian national character, contain information about the country. The selection, content and structure of the teaching material are aimed at helping foreigners form communicative, cultural and country study competences in Russian.

The cultural barrier is more unpleasant and dangerous than the linguistic one, the differences of cultures are not generalized to the same extent as the differences of languages. While grammatical errors on the part of foreigners in the environment of the target language are usually perceived good-naturedly, violations related to cultural ignorance make a negative impression. The RaFL teacher should strive for culturological education of students, to determine the volume and content of the cultural component depending on the stage and goals of training, to be careful in selection and presentation of such material. It is necessary to include in the preparation of foreign students more interesting texts about modern Russia, to talk not only about matryoshka, but also to show the attractive features of our contemporary - interest in education, sports, tourism, healthy lifestyles, outdoor recreation; to introduce such forms of youth art as bard songs, Grushin's festival, the Russian Student Spring Festival, etc. Cultural component, reference to the history of the country and Russian science contributes to the presentation of the vocabulary and grammar of the Russian language, its graphic and orthographic system in a historical perspective, in the broad context of the development of Russian written culture. Modern digital learning technologies allow active use of educational media resources, electronic equipment, databases of information and communication portals on the Russian language and other information resources.

Conclusions

Modern linguistics is developing in different directions, and is enriching the methodology of teaching RaFL with productive technologies and methods of organizing language material.

Contemporary RaFL teaching methodology is based on a comprehensive approach to the analysis of language activity, evaluating the communicative approach as the leading one and the methodological principles of communicative orientation arising from this approach. The task of systematization of speech material at different levels of proficiency in Russian as a foreign language can be effectively solved with the use of communicative-pragmatic complexes in the courses, which allow to present in unity the correlated in meaning and communicative role types of communicative situations, corresponding speech intentions and typical speech models. Their systematic description vividly demonstrates the peculiarities of Russian speech patterns in comparison with languages of other grammatical systems.

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